

Investigation of Li accumulations in LLZO based solid state batteries via *operando* neutron imaging and *ex-situ* correlative structural and chemical analysis

Luca Cressa^{a,b}, Pierre Boillat^{c,d}, Mathieu Gerard^a, Yanyan Sun^e, Sayantan Sharma^{a,f,*}, Olivier De Castro^a, Maryam Nojabaei^e, Guido Schmitz^b, Tom Wirtz^a, Santhana Eswara^a

^a Advanced Instrumentation for Nano-Analytics (AINA), Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology, 41 rue du Brill, L-4422 Belvaux, Luxembourg

^b Chair of Materials Physics, Institute for Materials Science, University of Stuttgart, Heisenbergstr. 3, 70569 Stuttgart, Germany

^c Laboratory for Neutron Scattering and Imaging (LNS), Paul Scherrer Institut (PSI), 5232 Villigen, Switzerland

^d Electrochemistry Laboratory (LEC), Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI), 5232 Villigen, Switzerland

^e German Aerospace Center (DLR), Institute of Engineering Thermodynamics, Pfaffenwaldring 38-40, 70569 Stuttgart, Germany

^f University of Luxembourg, 2 Avenue de l'Université, Esch-sur-Alzette, L-4365, Luxembourg

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ABSTRACT

In this study, we present a comprehensive analysis of lithium dendrite formation in half-cells with lithium garnet-type solid-state electrolyte $\text{Li}_7\text{La}_3\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_{12}$ (LLZO) utilizing *operando* neutron imaging and subsequent *ex-situ* correlative structural and chemical analysis. The *operando* experiment involves cycling a solid-state symmetric half-cell (Li|LLZO|Li) until short-circuit failure, all while being irradiated with neutrons, providing invaluable insights into the dynamic processes within the symmetric half-cell. Post-mortem investigations were carried out, comprising two techniques: 1) secondary electron imaging for structural analysis and 2) secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS) for chemical mapping. This multifaceted approach creates complementary datasets, bridging the gap between neutron radiography, known for its quantitative transmission capabilities, and high-resolution, high-sensitivity structural and chemical imaging via scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and SIMS.

Central to our investigation is the design and development of an *operando* neutron imaging approach, enabling the study of lithium penetration during the electrochemical cycling. Furthermore, structural, and chemical analyses through correlative SEM/SIMS unveil various morphologies of lithium accumulations. Specifically, regions with dense LLZO reveal intergranular lithium accumulations, while low-density areas within the LLZO pellet, such as pores and cracks, exhibit distinct types of lithium accumulations (e.g. whiskers).

Notably, neutron analysis reveals an accumulation of lithium in selected regions, with a maximum increase of up to 3.6 vol.-%. These regions primarily correspond to the roughened LLZO/Li interface, as observed through neutron imaging, although the SEM/SIMS analysis unequivocally confirms the presence of lithium dendrites (with sizes at or below the resolution limit of neutron imaging) also within the bulk of LLZO.

This work offers a comprehensive examination of the intricate dynamics of lithium dendrite formation and behaviour in LLZO-based solid-state half-cells, emphasizing the potential of *operando* techniques to advance our understanding of critical issues (e.g. degradation, dendrite formation, ...) in battery research.

1. Introduction

The upcoming global energy transition builds on green energy harvesting technologies and on reliable energy storage systems. Hence, the growing need and demand for efficient energy storage systems presents an essential milestone towards a greener society. Advanced battery

technologies, such as lithium-ion batteries, are playing a vital role in meeting this demand [1–5].

However, to this day crucial factors such as safety, lifetime and efficiency need to be improved in order to fulfil the needs of said energy transition. To study and better understand battery systems, advanced analysis and characterisation approaches are required. Scientists agree

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: sayantan.sharma@list.lu (S. Sharma).

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that static analyses (i.e. *ex-situ*) are not sufficient and *operando* analyses are needed [6–12].

Several studies have been carried out and scientists designed innovative set-ups for *operando* neutron experiments, for instance [13–17]. While L. Magnier et al. [15] performed an impressive study comparing neutron imaging with X-ray tomography to study Li electrodeposits, N.S. Nazer et al. [16] investigated commercial Li-ion batteries using *operando* neutron imaging. The approach enabled to track dynamic processes, aiding in the identification of performance limitations. However, their work is limited to (macroscopic) commercial ICR 10440 Li-ion cells. L.G. Butler et al. [13] also performed a creative *operando* neutron experiment on a commercial battery (prismatic lithium-ion polymer battery), but their approach is limited to large samples too, hence microstructural changes and degradations are not captured. On the other hand, D. Goers et al. [14] performed a study on *in-situ* neutron radiography of (non-commercial) Li-ion cells and especially focussing on understanding the gas evolution phenomenon occurring at graphite electrodes during the charging phase. They provided valuable information on the spatial and temporal distribution of gas evolution during charging, enhancing the comprehension of electrochemical processes. Insights gained from such studies can be crucial for optimizing battery design and performance, addressing potential safety concerns related to gas evolution. B. Song et al. [17] developed an impressive *operando* neutron imaging experiment, providing mechanistic insights with a deep understanding of dendrite Li shorting and redistribution. Unfortunately, their workflow misses a post-mortem analysis to directly prove the presence of Li dendrites.

Our methodology is based on an *operando* experiment of a solid-state half-cell which is cycled until short-circuit failure under neutron irradiation for analysis. Post-mortem investigation will be performed 1) via secondary electron imaging for structural analysis and 2) via secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS) for chemical mapping. Hence creating complementary data set between neutron radiography being a transmission method capable of quantitative analysis and correlative secondary electron (SE) and SIMS imaging allowing high resolution structural and high-resolution-high sensitivity chemical imaging. [18, 19]

The current study shows a correlative characterization approach aiming to bridge the gap between *operando* neutron imaging experiments and post-mortem structural and chemical analysis, by that overcoming analytical challenges. This work focusses on the distribution and redeposition of Li within the solid electrolyte, by that supporting electrochemists and battery researchers for an accelerated development of high-performance materials.

2. Materials and methods

For this proof of concept, $\text{Li}_7\text{La}_3\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_{12}$ (LLZO) powder from Jining CreaTech Energy Technology Co., Ltd, China, was used to produce the pellets. The LLZO pellets in this work were prepared using similar procedures as Zhang et al. [20], Jiang et al. [21] and Ganesh Kumar et al. [22] resulting in high density pellets (5.1 g/cm^3). After sintering, the pellets were polished using different sandpapers (grit number #4000) and have final dimensions of 11 mm in diameter and 1–1.5 mm in thickness. The metallic Li-foil which was used to assemble the half-cell was delivered by Alfa Aesar (CAS-No. 7439-93-2). No liquid electrolyte nor special pre-treatment on the Li foils were used in this work.

2.1. Sample preparation for *operando* neutron imaging

As the neutron beam penetrates through the cross-section of the sample and not through the thickness (see schematics of experimental configuration in SI Figure S2), it is important to design the symmetric half cell with a diameter as small as possible, to have penetration path which is small enough for neutrons to be transmitted. Hence the LLZO pellet was polished to a diameter of $\sim 4.6 \text{ mm}$ and a thickness of ~ 0.9

mm. Fig. 1 shows a 3D reconstruction of the Li- foils and the LLZO pellet.

2.2. Neutron tomo- and radiography

A detailed description of the design of the sample holder (Figure S1) as well as of the final experimental configuration (Figure S2) can be found in the Supporting Information (SI). After the preparation of the solid electrolyte half-cell sample (Li-LLZO-Li) and the proper placing inside the custom-designed sample holder, the latter was positioned between the neutron beamline and the detector to perform the experiment (Figure S2). The measurements were conducted at the ICON [23] (Imaging with Cold Neutrons) beam line of the SINQ neutron source at Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI). For the radiography measurement, a source aperture of 20 mm was used, resulting in a L/D ratio (length-to-diameter ratio) of 350 and a geometric blurring of approximately $50 \mu\text{m}$ for the sample detector distance of 19 mm. The neutron images were acquired using the micro-setup detector, featuring a field of view of $27 \times 27 \text{ mm}^2$ and a pixel size of $13.5 \mu\text{m}$. Upon impinging a scintillator screen made of $20 \mu\text{m}$ thick Tb doped $\text{Gd}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$ layer, neutrons generate light. The produced visible image was captured by a CCD camera (Andor Ikon-L, 2048×2048 pixels). The exposure time for single images was set to 30 s. For the tomography measurements, the source aperture was increased to 40 mm, resulting in a twofold increase of the geometric blur ($100 \mu\text{m}$) but allowing faster tomographies due to the increase of neutron flux. The tomographies were acquired using 125 angle steps distributed over 360° ($= 2.88^\circ$ per scan), resulting in a total acquisition time of approximately 1 hour.

2.3. Sample preparation for *ex-situ* SIMS analysis

After the *operando* neutron imaging experiment, the sample holder (including the sample) remained activated by neutron irradiation, meaning that the sample holder needed to be safely stored until the radioactive decay reached a non-critical level (\sim two weeks). In a subsequent step, the sample holder was opened inside an Ar-glove box ($[\text{O}_2] = \sim 0.6 \text{ ppm}$; $[\text{H}_2\text{O}] = \sim 0.8 \text{ ppm}$) and the sample was split in half in order to analyse the inside of the half-cell. Different preparation techniques for SEM/SIMS bulk analysis of solid-state batteries can be found elsewhere [24].

2.4. SIMS analysis

SIMS imaging was performed using a Thermo Fisher Scientific Scios DualBeam FIB-SEM equipped with an in-house developed double-focusing magnetic sector SIMS system which allows the detection of multiple masses in parallel [18,19]. The FIB consists of a gallium liquid metal ion source producing $^{69}\text{Ga}^+$ primary ions. The secondary ions that were collected and imaged are $^7\text{Li}^+$. The SIMS measurements were carried out with a primary ion beam energy of 30 keV, a beam current of 50 pA, and a dwell time of 0.5 ms per pixel. The images were recorded with a resolution of 512×512 pixels and fields of view around $20 \times 20 \mu\text{m}^2$. To extract positive secondary ions, the sample was biased to +500 V which resulted in a primary ion impact energy of 29.5 keV. Data analysis was performed using the free software ImageJ [25] and the commercial software AVIZO (Version 2021.1., Thermo Fisher Scientific).

2.5. Experimental workflow

The overall experimental workflow consists of:

- 1) Before cycling one neutron tomography measurement is performed (125 projections = 2.88° angle per scan) allowing to get a three-dimensional reconstruction of the pristine sample.
- 2) Two-dimensional radiography measurements are performed during the cycling of the battery until short-circuit failure (*operando*).

Fig. 1. Exemplary 3D reconstruction of the Li/LLZO/Li sample generated from the neutron tomography data.

- 3) After the short-circuit failure another tomography measurement is performed (identical experimental conditions), to have a three-dimensional comparison between pristine and short-circuited sample.
- 4) Correlative SEM and SIMS imaging (surface sensitive) is performed.

The approach comes with a multitude of challenges, including in particular the presence of metallic Li in the sample requires the system to be always in a controlled atmosphere to prevent oxidation of Li. The overall experimental configuration as well as the sample holder design for the neutron imaging experiment can be seen in the SI. (Figure S1 & S2)

3. Results

3.1. Operando neutron radiography

Before *operando* radiography measurements could be performed, calibration measurements (open beam black body, open beam, dark current) needed to be performed. For radiography an exposure time of 30 s per measurement was chosen. The electrochemical cycling parameters were initially chosen to incite a short-circuit failure of the Li-LLZO-Li sample within 24 h with four different current density settings 5, 10, 20 and 40 $\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ and 12 cycles for each setting. One full cycle took 30 min, resulting in $4 \times 12 \times 30 \text{ min} = 24 \text{ h}$. However, as the half-cell did not short-circuit after 24 h, it was decided to increase the current density to force a failure of the half cell. One cycle with a current density of 80 $\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ and two cycles with a current density of 160 $\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ were added. Fig. 2a) shows the voltage profile (black) and the current (red) as a function of time. Small alterations of the voltage profile are noticeable between 19 and 20 h (cycle: 39–40) which seems to recover in the following cycles (41–44 \rightarrow time = 21–22.5 h), coming back to expected voltage profile. From cycle 45 on, the voltage profile changes and did not recover until short-circuit at cycle 50. The last cycle (51) was performed to test whether the sample is fully short-circuited or if it will recover.

Fig. 2b) shows neutron radiographs at different stages of the experiment, at the 1st, 15th, 31st and 50th cycle, respectively. The big bright dot visible in all radiographs results from using a black body grid with Gadolinium dots, having the highest neutron attenuation among all elements, which is necessary for the correction of systematic biases such as scattered neutrons and other sources such as light reflections in the detector system [26]. The two highlighted regions on the left half of the sample (cyan and green box), show considerable change of the optical density (O.D.) during cycling.

The right side of the pellet does not show any evolution of the optical density during cycling, at least not for larger regions. The diagrams in Fig. 2c) & d) show the relative change of optical density during the cycling (time resolution = 30 min resulting in 52 data points) elucidating an increase (between first and last datapoint) by a factor of 12 (cyan box in c) and factor 16 (green box in d). A 2nd experiment was carried out to insure reproducibility and reliability of our custom-

Fig. 2. Operando neutron imaging. a) Voltage profile (black) and applied current densities (red): four different current density settings 5, 10, 20 and 40 $\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ were employed with 12 cycles for each. Three additional cycles, one with a current density of 80 $\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ and two cycles with a current density of 160 $\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ were added to force a short-circuit of the half-cell. b) Radiographs of the half-cell at different stages of the operando experiment, at the 1st, 15th, 31st and 50th cycle, respectively. The highlighted regions (cyan and green box) represent regions with the most alteration of the O.D. during the cycling. c) & d) Diagrams of $\Delta\text{O.D.}$ as a function of time (i.e. cycles), the cyan highlighted region (c) shows an increase from the first (0.0026) to the last data point (0.0309) by a factor of 12 and the green highlighted region (d) shows a relative increase of a factor 16.

designed experimental set-up. The additional neutron *operando* experiment was performed with 14 cycles ($\sim 7 \text{ h}$), followed by post-mortem SEM/SIMS analysis (see SI Figure S3). The reason for the different number of cycles of both experiments is purely related to the limited beam-time availability. Post-mortem analysis uncovered comparable Li-degradation artefacts in both samples, ensuring reproducibility.

3.2. Li quantification

To relate the optical density to the volume fraction of lithium in the electrolyte, the following calculation was conducted. The effective transmission through the sample can be calculated as [27]:

$$\frac{I}{I_0} = \frac{\int I_0(E) \cdot c_{eff}(E) \cdot e^{-[\Sigma_{el}(E) + \Phi \cdot \Sigma_{Li}(E)] \cdot d} \cdot dE}{\int I_0(E) \cdot c_{eff}(E) \cdot dE} \quad (1.1)$$

Where $I_0(E)$ is the beam spectrum (energy dependent intensity), $c_{eff}(E)$ is the energy dependent detector capture efficiency, $\Sigma_{el}(E)$ is the neutron linear attenuation coefficient of the electrolyte, $\Sigma_{Li}(E)$ is the neutron linear attenuation coefficient of lithium, Φ is the volume fraction of lithium dendrites and d is the thickness of the electrolyte in the direction of the neutron beam.

$$O.D. = -\ln\left(\frac{I}{I_0}\right) \quad (1.2)$$

Based on the electrolyte composition ($\text{Li}_7\text{La}_3\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_{12}$) with a density of $5.16 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ and using the energy dependent neutron attenuation cross sections of Li, La, Zr and O from the ENDF VIII database [28], the energy dependent linear attenuation coefficients of the electrolyte could be computed, as reported in Fig. 3.

The neutron linear attenuation coefficient of the electrolyte as a function of energy (Fig. 3a), shows the contribution of the different elements of LLZO. The diagram elucidates that Li in the LLZO crystal structure has the main contribution regarding neutron attenuation. Fig. 3b) demonstrates the linear attenuation coefficient as a function of the volume fraction of Li dendrites present within the electrolyte. Based on Eq. (1.1), the change of optical density (absolute O.D. & the transmission) could be computed for the ICON beam line as a function of Li dendrite volume fraction, assuming an average electrolyte thickness of 4 mm in the direction of the neutron beam (corresponding to the central section of the round shape electrolyte disk) (Fig. 4).

The values of $\Delta O.D./O.D.$ in Fig. 4 can be used to evaluate the excess Li volume fractions responsible for the changes observed in the radiographs (Fig. 2c, d & Fig. 5). For instance, according to our calculations, regions in the radiographic images with a 2 % increase in O.D. can be interpreted as excess in Li of $\sim 1.5 \%$.

Battery degradations can occur very locally and one single dendritic filament can in theory short-circuit the battery. The spatial resolution of the ICON beamline does not allow to detect single sub-micron scale dendrites, however larger ($>20 \mu\text{m}$) localized Li accumulations can be spotted.

Fig. 3. (a) Neutron linear attenuation coefficient of the electrolyte as a function of energy, showing the contribution of the different elements (b) Linear attenuation coefficient as a function of the Li dendrites volume fraction.

Fig. 4. Calculated transmission, optical density, and change of optical density as a function of the excess volume fraction of Li, for the ICON beam line and for an electrolyte thickness of 4 mm.

Fig. 5 shows a diagram of $\Delta O.D.$ as a function of cycles at localized regions, which were chosen for this evaluation (radiograph inset: 1 = violet; 2 = green; 3 = blue and 4 = black). In Fig. 2 as well as in Fig. 5 all the regions of considerable $\Delta O.D.$ are at the interface between Li and LLZO and show fluctuations of the O.D. between 0.025 and 0.060. This means that the excess Li volume fraction in those regions, which grew during cycling, is between 1.5 and 3.6 %. As mentioned above, usually dendrite formation and propagation are not homogeneous within batteries, hence a single dendritic connection from one electrode to the other can already cause short circuit failures. As the resolution of neutron imaging is only $\sim 30 \mu\text{m}$, only larger ($>20 \mu\text{m}$) Li-accumulations will become detectable by neutron imaging.

3.3. Post-mortem structural and chemical characterisation

The sample holder was introduced into a glove box before it could be opened and prepared as described elsewhere [24]. In the following, the

Fig. 5. Diagram of Δ O.D. as a function of cycles at localized regions. The regions which were chosen for this evaluation are shown in the radiograph inset (1 = violet; 2 = green; 3 = blue and 4 = black). All the regions of considerable Δ O.D. are at the interface between Li and LLZO and show alterations of the O.D. between 0.025–0.060 .

sample was transferred from the glove box to the FIB-SEM-SIMS instrument via an inert gas transfer system.

Secondary electron imaging immediately reveals that a compositional change must have occurred, as a second phase, different from LLZO becomes visible. Fig. 6 reveals in a) the dark phase (red arrow) which seems to be mostly located in intergranular spaces. b) and c) show two secondary electron images with smaller FOVs which clearly show that the dark phase is preferentially localised in grain boundaries. Additionally, chemical imaging via SIMS has been performed at the same locations as b) and c) elucidating that the dark phase which appeared as a consequence of cycling is Li-rich. While several researchers were able to observe similar degradation features after short-circuiting LLZO based batteries, only a few were able to directly prove the presence of Li in these phases.

While the images in Fig. 6 were taken from very dense bulk-regions of the LLZO, Fig. 8 shows images taken at the proximity of an internal crack in the bulk of the LLZO pellet. Fig. 7 shows a 3D reconstruction of the uncycled LLZO pellet, elucidating the presence of a large crack/pore

Fig. 7. 3-dimensional reconstruction of the pristine LLZO pellet based on the neutron tomography data. This cross section elucidates a dense material; however, one larger crack is visible in the centre of the pellet. SE/SIMS images from Fig. 6 were recorded in dense regions, while images in Fig. 8 were taken in the proximity of the crack (red arrow).

at a cross section through the bulk. Impurities or defects like pores and cracks are undesired, as they reduce the electrochemical performance and encourage parasitic reactions and Li-accumulations. It is unclear if this crack was produced during sample preparation for the neutron experiment or already when synthesising the pellet. It is just clear that the crack did not appear during cycling, as it could already be seen in the tomography of the uncycled half-cell.

To our surprise, different morphologies of the Li-rich phase could be observed inside of the crack. A SEM image with large FOV = 96 μm of the crack in the short circuited LLZO pellet is visible in Fig. 8a). The approximate position is indicated by the red arrow in Fig. 7. Li whiskers growing into the crack (red box in Fig. 8a) are demonstrated from two perspectives: side view (b) and top view (c). The presence of Li whiskers is highlighted by white dashed circles. A second rather bulky Li morphology is indicated by white arrows in b), c), and d). Fig. 8d) shows a region on the edge of the crack where again whiskers are visible, but more interestingly a pore ($\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$) which is filled by Li-rich material and possibly ready to extrude a whisker dendrite (small, dashed circle). e) shows a SIMS image of Li in the region indicated by the green box in d), proving that the whiskers as well as the bulky dendrites are Li-rich. The whiskers visible in the SEM images have an approximate height of 7 μm and individual filaments have a diameter $< 0.3 \mu\text{m}$ (which is below the resolution limit for neutron imaging, and hence not detected by that technique), even though it is difficult to determine the sizes precisely as bundles of filaments have formed.

Fig. 6. a) Secondary electron images recorded by ($^{69}\text{Ga}^+$) ion irradiation (LLZO - white arrow; Li - red arrow), and b & c) correlative secondary electron and chemical maps of $^7\text{Li}^+$.

Fig. 8. a) SE image with large FOV = 96 μm of the crack in the short circuited LLZO pellet. The approximate position is indicated by the red arrow in Fig. 7. b) (side view) and c) (top view) show a zoom-in of the region indicated by the red box in a). These images reveal the presence of whisker-like dendrites (white dashed circles) and a bulky morphology (white arrows). d) shows a region on the edge of the crack where again whiskers are visible, but more interestingly a pore ($\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$) which is filled by Li-rich material. e) shows a Li map of the region indicated by the green box in d).

In conclusion, we were able to observe three different Li-dendrites morphologies within the same sample.

1. Intergranular Li accumulations as observed in Fig. 6 in high density regions.
2. Thin whiskers growing out of grain boundaries in cracks.
3. Bulky Li-accumulations in pores and cracks.

3.4. Limitations

Given that our findings are based on a limited number of analysed samples, interpretations should be treated with caution. Blondeau et al. [29] for instance discusses the reliability of *operando* measurements in rechargeable batteries during *operando* synchrotron X-ray radiation. In summary they demonstrated that the interaction between synchrotron X-rays and the cells not only modified the electrode but also entirely invalidated the electrode processes right from the initial cycles. This shows that utmost caution must be taken when performing and interpreting *operando* experiments. Beam-related (neutrons as well as ions) artefacts might occur, which have not been studied neither considered in this study, thus we don't know yet if their effect is significant or negligible. Like synchrotron X-rays, neutron irradiation could alter or influence electrochemical processes or induce parasitic cross-reactions or both. However, neutrons used for imaging generally are of low energy (meV range) and neutron fluxes are significantly lower compared to fluxes used in synchrotrons. Thus, the possibility of beam related damage is comparatively less for neutron imaging.

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, this study represents a significant step forward in understanding the complex phenomena surrounding lithium dendrites in solid-state batteries. Our multifaceted approach, combining *operando* neutron imaging with *ex-situ* correlative structural and chemical analysis, has yielded valuable insights into the formation, behaviour, and distribution of lithium accumulations within the half-cell.

Our *operando* neutron imaging technique has allowed for real-time monitoring of lithium penetration during electrochemical cycling, providing crucial data on the dynamics of dendrite growth and its spatial distribution. The subsequent *ex-situ* analyses, employing secondary electron imaging for structural analysis and SIMS for chemical mapping, have further enriched our understanding of the system. By combining quantitative transmission capabilities of neutron radiography with the

high-resolution, high-sensitivity structural and chemical imaging capabilities of SEM/SIMS, we have generated complementary datasets, offering a comprehensive view of the battery's internal processes.

By combining a quantitative transmission technique (*operando* neutron imaging) with a surface-sensitive structural and chemical analysis (post-mortem SEM/SIMS), analytical challenges related to only one-sided analysis could be tackled, bridging the gap between *operando* neutron experiments and post-mortem analysis.

Our results underscore the diverse morphologies of lithium accumulations, highlighting intergranular lithium accumulation in dense LLZO regions, in contrast to the various types of accumulations (whiskers and mossy) observed in low-density areas. Moreover, the significant excess of lithium in specific regions, reaching up to 3.6 %, is a striking revelation that draws attention to the importance of controlling dendrite growth for the long-term stability of solid-state batteries.

This study highlights the potential of *operando* methodologies and their critical role in advancing battery research. It sheds light on the complexities of lithium dendrite formation, distribution, and behaviour, ultimately contributing to the development of safer and more efficient solid-state batteries, which are vital for the future of energy storage technologies.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Luca Cressa: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Pierre Boillat:** Validation, Resources, Methodology. **Mathieu Gerard:** Methodology. **Yanyan Sun:** Resources. **Sayantana Sharma:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Olivier De Castro:** Resources, Methodology. **Maryam Nojabae:** Resources. **Guido Schmitz:** Writing – review & editing. **Tom Wirtz:** Writing – review & editing. **Santhana Eswara:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.electacta.2024.144397](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2024.144397).

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